

ReMovAble (GLOVE)

Hand Assistive Exoskeleton for Activities of Daily Life

Project developed at

*Advanced Material & Design Laboratory, Dept. Industrial Engr. (DIN),
with the aid of the Dept. of Electrical, Electronic & Information Engr. (DEI),
of the School of Engineering and Architecture of the University of Bologna,
in collaboration with the Montecatone Rehabilitation Institute*

Report by

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1. State of the Art

This report consolidates the research, design, and development efforts undertaken within the GLOVE project, a collaborative initiative between the University of Bologna and the Montecatone Rehabilitation Institute. The goal of the GLOVE project is to develop a functional and user-friendly hand exoskeleton to assist tetraplegic patients, specifically those with C6-C7 level spinal cord injuries, in performing Activities of Daily Living by restoring a degree of hand mobility.

This document aims to synthesise the **key findings, requirements, and objectives** identified across multiple student theses and research work associated with the project. It is intended to serve as a comprehensive reference for future researchers, designers, and engineers who will continue the development of the GLOVE exoskeleton, ensuring continuity and building upon the valuable work already accomplished. The report is structured to provide a clear understanding of the problem, the evolving requirements, and the targeted objectives across the main subsystems: the control **signal** system, the **actuation** system, and the physical **exoskeleton** design.

The definition of objectives and requirements for the exoskeleton's development requires a clear understanding of its journey thus far. Therefore, we will start with a brief chronological overview of the project in the following section.

1.1. Chronicle: overview of exoskeleton development

2020–Clinic encounter

Through Prof. Francesco Cesari's contact with **Dr. Silvia Olivi**, a meeting is arranged between Prof. Andrea Zucchelli, Gregorio Pisaneschi, Dr. Olivi and Dr. Kiekens Carlote¹, the chief of the spinal unit of the **Montecatone Rehabilitation Institute S.p.A.** (<https://www.montecatone.com/>). They requested the creation of an assistive device to help quadriplegic patients use their hands in everyday gestures (e.g., grasping objects, such as a water bottle). From the state-of-the-art analysis, the commercial devices present were expensive and were designed to increase functionality, such as the SEM glove². On the other hand, there were prototypes that would have the potential to meet the needs, but about which no information could be found³, or that it is still not available⁴. The informal collaboration between the clinic and the university to design and implement a functional device was born.

¹ Nowadays, the chief is Dr. Laura Simoncini

² A Swedish project, nowadays known as Carbonhand by Bioservo, which is commercially available

³ Contacted by the clinic, the Korean research group developing the Exo-Glove Poly never answered. They demonstrated the functionality of the system, but the development of the design seems to have stopped

⁴ Tenoexo from ETH. A contact was established in 2023 (Gregorio with Prof. Lambercy), and the project seemed to be ready for commercialisation (the research has been dismissed), but there is no news yet.

a) Exo-Glove Poly II

Soft Rob. Lab (KR)
Since 2010
Practical to dress
Simple design
Unguided Closure
Silicone wearing
Next: Intention detect

H. Lee, B. B. Kang, H. In, and K.-J. Cho, "Design Improvement of a Polymer -Based Tendon -Driven Wearable Robotic Hand (Exo -Glove Poly)," in *Wearable Robotics: Challenges and Trends* . doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-46532-6_16. <https://www.srrc.snu.ac.kr/>

b) SEM-Glove

Bioservo (SE)
Since 2012
Compact design
Lot of Clinical Trial
Unguided Closure
Only increase force (+20N)
Available for clinics (SE,DE,US)

R. HASHIDA et al., "Evaluation of Motor -Assisted Gloves (SEM Glove) for Patients with Functional Finger Disorders: A Clinical Pilot Study," *Kurume Med. J.*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 63 -70, Jun. 2018. <https://www.bioservo.com/healthcare>

c) Tenoexo

ETH Relab (CH)
Since 2013
Guided closure
All external + tumb
Cost? Comfort?
Next: commercialization?

T. Bützer, O. Lamercy, J. Arata, and R. Gassert, "Fully Wearable Actuated Soft Exoskeleton for Grasping Assistance in Everyday Activities," *Soft Robot.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 128-143, 2021. <https://relab.ethz.ch/research/current-research-projects/robotic-hand-orthosis-for-therapy-and-assistance-in-activities-of-daily-living.html>

Figure 1 Main assistive solution

2021-Prototype ZERO

The project kicks off through the thesis work of **Mattia Tarsi** (Bachelor of Electronics), who developed the electronics with the assistance of the researcher Davide Raggini (Prof. Andrea Tilli). Following a meeting with the clinic, the main requirements for device design were defined. The study of the state of the art began: existing devices, standards for design, and scientific articles.

A Meeting with the clinic takes place next, in which Paola Pagliarini also participates, who provided the video in which a patient's motor skills (see Problem Statement section) are demonstrated. The main elements of the device are then defined:

- I. **Cable drive** with **electric motor**
- II. Control via **Arduino** platform
- III. Use of **myosignals** for activation (via a bracelet, MYO Armband)
- IV. Design of a **hybrid soft-rigid exoskeleton** with compliant joints (springs).

The last innovative element is intended to use designed flexures to act as a return spring that returns the hand to the open position and guides it in the closing movement. The other solutions were chosen for their effectiveness, implementability and cost-effectiveness.

Work on the first prototype, **GLOVE ZERO**, was completed by Mattia. The concept of this first prototype is the creation of a base, electromechanical, on which to carry out subsequent experiments, consisting of a control platform, a motor and a pulley. It's a tendon-driven actuation system using a **DC motor** with gear reduction, an encoder, controlled by an **Arduino Nano 33 BLE Sense** via a full-bridge driver and a current sensor for monitoring. Functionally, Prototype ZERO could be manually controlled by push buttons to drive the motor, change its direction, and manage its speed through PWM, with its operational data, including voltage and current readings, being verifiable via serial communication and direct measurements. It had been tested to generate forces up to 55N and provided a modifiable platform for further experimentation, particularly in control logic and data acquisition, though it uses an external power supply as battery integration is a future step.

Figure 2 Prototype ZERO

Meanwhile, as part of the **SMAtronic** project, a group of automation engineering students realised a device made with an actuation system using shape memory alloys

(SMAs). The project showed the potential and limitations of using such alloys for the actuation. SMA have advantages of being silent, compact and strong compared to the size (e.g. 15N for a 0.2 mm diameter wire), with huge disadvantages due to speed of deactivation (cooling), heating, insulation, control accuracy (hysteresis), and stroke limitation (3-5% of the length of the wire as maximum shape memory deformation).

Figure 3 SMATronic project students' prototype

2022–Prototype UNO

Tommaso Ferrero and **Valerio** Giannini (Bachelor of Automation Engineering) worked on design with Prof. Nicola Sancisi and EMG signals with Prof. Roberto Diversi, respectively. The first draft of the design is made. You have at the bottom the loops where the wire for implementing the grip will pass, and at the top the compliant joints that connect the elements that will be inserted into the finger. Tommaso focused on the analysis and design of **compliant joints** using FEM to evaluate stress, strain, and the ideal geometry (circular, elliptical, modified) to ensure they function effectively and minimize stress on the user's joints by aligning their center of curvature with the natural joint rotation.

Figure 4 First design of the exoskeletal part of the finger with compliant joints and open rings

Three students (Bachelor of Automation Engineering) joined the project: **Eleonora** Valeri, **Mirco** Paltrinieri and **Ivano** De Paola, in charge of, respectively, the design and prototyping of the UNO prototype, the control of the motor and the implementation of the control with myoelectric signals, followed respectively by Gregorio Pisaneschi, Prof. Davide Samorì and PhD. Matteo Barbieri.

Figure 5 Prototype UNO

The work on **myoelectric signals**, carried out by Valerio and Ivano, had produced good results. The prospect of using such signals, taken from the arm, is feasible, given what was seen with a healthy person. Valerio focused on an in-depth investigation of EMG signals from the bicep, acquired using a **Myo Armband** and analysed in MATLAB. He collected data from both healthy subjects and tetraplegic patients, compared various signal processing techniques like Filter-Rectify-Envelope, **RMS**, and a first-order filter, and critically assessed the feasibility of a simple threshold-based **ON/OFF** control logic. His findings highlighted that while EMG signals from patients were suitable for control, this approach was prone to errors due to movement artefacts reaching intensities similar to intentional isometric contractions. Ivano then undertook the practical implementation of the sensor system for the "prototipo UNO". He designed the direct BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy) interface between the Myo and the Arduino Nano and developed a **real-time threshold-based algorithm** on the Arduino to translate detected bicep contractions into ON/OFF commands. Ivano's system also incorporated a manual threshold mechanism to adapt to individual users.

Figure 6 Myoelectric signals acquisition system

In parallel, Eleonora integrated research on sensor systems (by Valerio and Ivano) and motor control (by Mirco) into a functional unit, the UNO prototype. Started with a **kinematic model** of the human hand and fingers developed in MATLAB to define tendon pathways and their placements in the rings, and calculated necessary tendon **displacements for finger flexion**. The exoskeleton utilised a **tendon-driven actuation** mechanism powered by a Faulhaber DC motor with gearbox and a magnetic encoder. The gear motor was coupled with a **pulley distribution system** to achieve the required force and motion profile. The physical realization of the prototype involved CAD/FEM design (Creo, ANSYS) and 3D printing of finger rings and TPU compliant joints. The sensor input from a Myo Armband was processed by an Arduino Nano, and the motor control was managed by an Arduino UNO with a Motor Shield employing PID control. The prototype UNO was experimentally tested, demonstrating its capability to grasp various objects.

Figure 7 Parametric model of the hand

2022–Prototype DUE-0

The motor was a **Faulhaber DC micromotor** Series 2232 012 SR with a 152:1 planetary **gearbox** and a Series IE2-1024 **magnetic encoder**, a coreless brushed offering low inertia and no cogging torque.

Mirco's primary contribution was the design and realisation of a **robust feedback control** system to manage the exoskeleton's hand opening and closing movements. He employed a **cascaded** control architecture consisting of an outer position loop, a

middle velocity loop, and an inner current (torque) loop. This structure was implemented using **PID** controllers (specifically PI for current and velocity, and PD for position), with parameters tuned based on the mathematical model of the chosen DC motor and desired closed-loop time constants, ensuring separation of dynamics between the loops. Mirco simulated the cascaded control system in MATLAB Simulink, including controller discretisation and **anti-windup** strategies. The control algorithms were **discretised using Tustin's method** for digital implementation on an Arduino Due microcontroller. The **Arduino Due** was selected for its processing capabilities and, critically, its hardware quadrature encoder counters, which were necessary to accurately read the high-frequency signals from the motor's encoder. An H-bridge driver (Arduino **Motor Shield Rev3** based on L298) was required to supply the necessary power to the motor, controlled by **PWM** signals from the microcontroller. Mirco conducted experimental validation on a custom test bench with variable loads, and finally by integrating the control system with the prototype DUE exoskeleton, which employs Bowden cable transmission (for instance, bicycle gear shift and brakes use Bowden cable).

Figure 8 a) cascaded control architecture; b) load (kg) – tension (V) experimental relationship

Next, **Marilyn** Mabel Gilbert designed, realised, and tested the implementation of **Bowden cables** and a “GLOVE” for the hand with superelastic compliant joints in prototype DUE, with the help of Gregorio for the design and Mirco for the actuation. Marilyn's design also incorporated a **pulley distribution system** for the partitioning of the actuation force from a single motor output to these fingers. The physical prototype included 3D-printed components of the glove structure and the **guiding channels** for

the cables on the palm, and a shaped Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) wire on the side of the fingers to assist with passive extension.

Marylin's work documents the modelling of hand kinematics, the design of cable pathways through tendon pathways, and the detailed prototyping process. Experimental testing of the assembled prototype DUE demonstrated its capability to perform grasping tasks with different objects, producing a grip force of approximately 9 Newtons. The required shortening for the finger was between 12 and 18 mm.

Figure 9 Tendon pathways points of entrance and exit

Figure 10 The distribution pulleys, the Bowden cables and the glove (detail on the superelastic joints)

2023–Prototype DUE-1, ReMovAble

Ornella Roccaforte, supervised by Mattia Mele, presented a user-centred design and prototyping strategy and proposed the name "**Removable**". She did a Quality Function Deployment (**QFD**) analysis to capture and prioritise the needs of both patients and medical professionals. Three primary engineering and design targets were identified as most crucial: achieving **compactness of dimensions** for better ease of use and wearability; the **use of lightweight materials** enhancing comfort, portability, and reducing physical strain on the user; and the implementation of a **modular design** to satisfy needs related to maintainability, adaptability for future upgrades.

Based on these requirements, Roccaforte developed the "Removable" concept. A prototype was developed using multimaterial 3D printing (Material Jetting). In particular,

she developed the concept of a **flexible palmar structure** designed for **ergonomic fit** and secured with Velcro straps for easy "top-down" application and finger segments composed of 3D-printed semi-open rings connected by flexible joints.

Figure 11 Removable design, details of the Bowden cables box and the above open structure of rings and joints

2023–Prototype DUE-2, Grabable

Hugo van der Linden's project, supervised by Nicola Sancisi, focused on designing and developing a **patient-specific** hand exoskeleton (Christian volunteered), the first functional prototype tested. The design focus was on improving finger guidance and the spring-back mechanism compared to previous GLOVE project iterations.

Concept Development. Hugo generated six initial concepts for the finger bending and return mechanism. After presenting these, the "**sliding** concept", where flexures extend during finger bending, was chosen for further development.

Iterative Design of Flexures and Rings. He explored various configurations, including flexures with additional arches, to optimize stress distribution and deflection, using FEM simulations and physical model testing on a **3D photogrammetry-scanned model** of the patient's hand. His tests concluded that sliding elements for each phalanx were more efficient than a full strip over the finger due to friction. The finger rings underwent significant design changes. Initial designs faced challenges with breathability and cable routing. The final iteration adopted a triangular structure, and the cable guide tunnels were repositioned to prevent contact with the finger.

Hand Attachment and Thumb Mechanism. The overall hand attachment was designed using elastic bands and Velcro for ease of application and a secure fit, evolving from testing various partial solutions.

Prototyping and testing. The prototype components were 3D-printed using ABS-like resin. The design also incorporated **grip strips** on the rings to prevent objects from

slipping. The final prototype was tested with the patient, demonstrating relative ease of installation by nurses, effective finger return, good bending mechanics, and gripping.

Figure 12 Left, 3D scanned hand and measurement of the patient's hand; right, design sketches

Figure 13 Tests at the clinic with Cristian. a) exoskeleton dressed, b) testing of the system, video

2023–Superelastic Bowden, preliminary tests

In **Gregorio's** doctoral thesis project, in collaboration with the InBio biomechanics research group at the University of Elche, the application of **shape memory alloys (SMA)** was developed and studied. In particular, the use of this material, because of its super-elastic properties and hysteretic behaviour, was conceptualised for compliant joints and was tested for transmission in Bowden cable (Figure 14 b). He experimentally validated a **Bowden cable** system that utilises **superelastic (SE) Nitinol SMA** wires. The research experimentally demonstrates that SE SMA wires significantly **reduce friction** to approximately one-quarter that of traditional stainless steel cables and nearly double the mechanical efficiency within Bowden cable transmissions under cyclic loading conditions. Moreover, it was demonstrated that, by **monitoring the electrical**

resistance of the SE Nitinol wire, the system can accurately **detect overloads** and collisions within 1% force error. Furthermore, the passive force **self-limiting** behaviour intrinsic to SE SMA wires was demonstrated. During impacts or excessive loads, the material undergoes a stress-induced martensitic transformation, causing the transmitted force to plateau, which **mimics the protective lengthening reflex** of biological tendons, enhancing user safety.

Figure 14 a) hysteretic behaviour of a superelastic wire; b) possible application in bowden cables or as flexure

Figure 15 Experiment with force threshold: a) force and electrical resistance over time, b) force vs resistance over cycles. Experiment with resistance threshold: c) values at motor inversion after reaching the threshold

Figure 16 Scheme of the patent of the exoskeleton system with the superelastic Bowden cable

2024–Prototype TRE

Giacomo Pala's (supervised by Mattia Mele) work built upon previous prototypes by Hugo and Ornella. Pala's research updated Ornella's previous QFD analysis. His design objectives included ergonomics, cleanability, accessibility, and comfort for prolonged use. Pala's developed a wearable glove structure with **integrated guides** for Bowden cables and a **pattern for breathability**, and the upgrade of the design of a Bowden cable termination box, prototyped by 3D printing with ABS-like resin.

Figure 17 Giacomo's design of the exoskeleton with the Bowden cable box (black) and the tutor structure (teal)

To overcome Myo ArmBand limitations (e.g., designed for the forearm, Bluetooth, battery), and the fact that it's no longer commercially available, it was decided that a **custom-developed analog EMG acquisition system** was required. **Lorenzo** Fantazzini, under the supervision of Carlo Gotti, contributed to the hardware design of the custom EMG acquisition circuit and the development of software for signal conditioning, analysis, and pattern recognition using a state machine approach. The analog signal processing chain, simulated in Matlab/Simulink and physically prototyped, includes **differential amplification** (using INA118), a 50Hz **notch filter**, and a 400Hz **low-pass filter**, with a DC offset for Arduino ADC compatibility.

The digital processing involves **RMS** calculation of the EMG signal to quantify muscle contraction levels. The software, written in C++ with Object-Oriented Programming (OOP) principles, uses a **state machine to recognise specific contraction patterns** (e.g., one long contraction for hand closure, two distinct short contractions for opening). Experimental testing with a patient revealed a key challenge: **distinguishing intentional EMG commands from muscle activity** during functional arm movements when using the bicep of the active arm. Tests indicated that using the contralateral (left) bicep provided clearer, more reliable command signals. A **PCB** version of the custom sensor was then developed (working in progress).

Figure 18 a) the circuit, b) position of the electrode, c) state machine, d) PCB

Marcello Ori, supervised by Alessandro Bosso and Davide Samorì, built upon the motor control work done by Mirco on the control of the motor. Marcello introduced and detailed the design of an **impedance control loop** as an additional layer to the Micro cascaded control system for position, velocity, and current (torque). He also detailed a more explicit consideration of Back-Electromotive Force compensation in the controller design.

Eleonora Poltrini, under the supervision of Gregorio and Nicola, focused on mechanical design and prototyping aimed at improving the wearability, stability, and comfort of the glove component. Poltrini adapted and utilised existing Matlab code (from Eleonora Valeri's prior work) to perform **kinematic and force analysis** based on the specific **patient's hand measurements** (calculating tendon shortenings of ~12-17mm and a required cable force of ~90N, considering friction). Using 3D scan data of the patient's hand for a **custom fit**, Eleonora developed the **palm and dorsal support structures** (printed using ABS-like photopolymer resin), refined finger rings (based on Hugo's design but thickened for rigidity), and a system for **fixing the thumb with a tutor** (commercial component). Initial testing with the patient focused on fitting and comfort, leading to a **functional prototype** that demonstrated improved hand support and ease of wearing compared to previous versions, though further refinements for durability and thumb articulation were identified as future work.

Figure 19 a) modeling of the forces, b) design of the palmar plate, considering the space requirements and the embedding of the cable pathways, c) exoskeleton completed with the thumb tutor, d) test at the clinic

2025–Prototype QUATTRO

Significant efforts were directed toward optimising the mathematical modelling and control architecture of the actuation system. **Maria Francesca Saporetti** (Bachelor in Automation Engineering), supervised by **Prof. Nicola Sancisi** and **Gregorio Pisaneschi**, focused on the analytical optimisation of the tendon actuation and the validation of the mathematical model. Her work refined the **mathematical model** of the finger mechanism by integrating a detailed **kinematic** analysis and improving predictive calculations for critical parameters, including the required motor torque and the resulting **finger tip force**. She designed and prototyped a physical model using specific geometric measurements from the target patient, defined experimental protocols to test finger kinematics and fingertip force, and executed the **validation experiments** to verify the mathematical model (Figure 20). The tip force test, measured for cable forces of 5 N and 10 N, showed maximum errors of 23% and 37%, respectively.

Figure 20 a) on the left scheme of the analytical kinematics model, in the centre, the graphic results obtained from the mathematical model and obtained from the experiments, and on the right, the experimental measures; b) on the left scheme of the analytical model for finger tip force, on the right, experiment with the loadcell

Concurrently, **Andrea D'Agostino** (Bachelor in Automation Engineering), supervised by Gregorio Pisaneschi, Carlo Gotti, and **Alessandro Bosso**, worked on the design and validation of the motor control system. Building on Mirco's previous cascaded control architecture (position, velocity, and current loops), D'Agostino **refined PID controller** tuning to achieve greater accuracy and closer alignment between simulated models and the real prototype's dynamics. His work included implementing an **impedance control loop** as an additional outer layer of the cascaded system, enhancing the exoskeleton's ability to manage compliant interactions under variable load conditions. D'Agostino discretised the control algorithms for real-time implementation on an Arduino Due microcontroller, addressing practical challenges in timing management and signal processing.

Cristian Eduardo Scutti (Internship), supervised by Gregorio Pisaneschi and **Eng. Lucia Ricci** at the Montecatone Rehabilitation Institute addressed the critical EMG intent-detection issues of signal robustness and integration. He researched a hardware optimisation campaign to ensure signal integrity in electrically noisy environments. He

evaluated different shielding strategies for the custom sensor designed by Lorenzo. The sensor was validated by testing the system under varying mechanical loads at two different electrode positions. An example of the mapped surface EMG signals to discrete hand states using a finite-state machine is shown.

Figure 21 surface EMG test with a custom sensor, comparison between two different positions for the electrodes

2025-Superelastic Bowden, extensive tests

Giorgio Giaretta (Bachelor of Automation Engineering) supervised and, in collaboration with **Carlo Gotti** and **Gregorio Pisaneschi**, conducted an extensive **experimental characterisation of the patented SE Bowden cable transmission system**. Preliminary different SMA wire diameters (0.2 mm, 0.3 mm, 0.5 mm) were **electro-mechanically characterised** by monotonic and cyclic tensile testing using custom-built testing equipment. Then, to test the Bowden system, an **advanced test setup** with Arduino and MATLAB software architecture was designed and built. The setup (Figure 22a) comprised a force measurement as an input and output of the Bowden system, and used different wires with different bending angles. The experiments validated the SE wires' implementation of a predictive force-resistance model enabling **sensorless force control** and **resistance-based feedback control** in scenarios mimicking real exoskeleton use. The tests confirmed that SE Bowden cables can accurately **detect force transmission and overload conditions by monitoring electrical resistance**, with force estimation accuracy within **1% error** without external load cells.

Furthermore, Pisaneschi's experiments also demonstrated **stainless steel sensing capability** by electrical resistance.

Figure 22 a) Scheme of the Bowden system testing setup; b) Results comparison with loading cycles of the system using load cell force control and force control using the electrical resistance.

To support this advanced control strategy, **Andrea Alessi** (Master's internship of Automation Engineer) developed a dedicated **high-precision electronic sensing** circuit. His design employed the 4-wire Kelvin measurement technique, managed by an STM32 microcontroller, to accurately monitor the low electrical resistance of the SMA wires (on the order of a few Ohms). This hardware solution effectively eliminated errors caused by lead and contact resistances, ensuring the signal integrity required for robust sensing algorithm performance.

1.2. Dissemination, Impact and Valorisation Strategy

The transition of ReMovAble from an academic prototype to a deployable clinical solution requires a strategy that goes beyond engineering. The strategy operated on:

1. Rigorous peer review in highly specialised domains, in **specialised symposia** and **scientific journals**, to certify the reliability of the core technology.
2. Securing the project's commercial future through **intellectual property protection** and creating a compelling **public narrative** by the Media to attract industrial interest.
3. Defining a fully costed, **laboratory and clinical execution plan**, quantifying the resources required for development and validation with patient trials.

2023-AlmaValue

To bridge the gap between prototype and product, **Pisaneschi** structured a 12-month **validation roadmap** targeting the *AlmaValue* Proof of Concept funding. The initiative proposed a pilot study to test the device in a relevant environment (Figure 23), backed by a consortium comprising **UniBo**, **Montecatone Institute** (Clinical Trials), and **INAIL**

(Regulatory/Safety), with a total budget estimation of approximately **€70,000**, covering research personnel, hardware manufacturing, and clinical validation. The proposal successfully passed technical screening and advanced to the **Final Pitch**, validating the solidity of the management plan and the consortium structure. However, the final evaluation penalised the project because the **patent** was listed as a *deliverable*, whereas the investment committee preferred it as a *prerequisite*.

Figure 23 Final pitch deck for the AlmaValue proof of concept

2024-Intellectual Property & Public Engagement

Following the committee's feedback, the project pivoted to patent the superelastic Bowden cable sensing system. In June 2024, to secure commercial rights, **Pisaneschi filed a patent** with the University of Bologna protecting the core "Sensing" technology. This legal instrument covers the use of the superelastic wire as both an efficient self-limiting transmission system and a sensor for force and overload detection. Application No: **102024000017122**; Title: **Exoskeleton and Method for Operating an Exoskeleton**; Site: <https://www.unibo.it/it/con-societa-e-impresa/impres-e-non-profit/brevetti-ateneo/brevetti-ateneo/scheda/2528>

Concurrently, the University of Bologna released the video "**Meet Gregorio Pisaneschi - Engineering with Heart**". This campaign translated the technical innovation into a social impact narrative, publicly validating the collaboration with the Montecatone Institute and the device's "human-like" tendon behaviour. The video was published in the media of the university.

www.youtube.com/watch?v=kvhuRHvX2GQ&ab_channel=Universit%C3%A0diBologna

2024-ESOMAT Symposium

European Symposium on Martensitic Transformations, July 2024, Lecco (IT).

Contribution: *"Improving Soft Robotic Systems to Enable Hand Mobility: Integration of a Pseudo-Elastic Bowden cable and Digital Twin-Driven Design."* This submission presented the exoskeleton project, specifically the superelastic Bowden cable system, specifically a Finite Element Analysis (FEA) model for the theoretical understanding of the superelastic wire's stress response.

2025-Scientific publication, IEEE RA-L

The technical validation was achieved with the publication of **"Superelastic Tendon-Like Bowden Cables: Advancing Assistive Exoskeletons"** in **IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters**, Oct. 2025, (<https://doi.org/10.1109/LRA.2025.3605094>). This top-tier peer review transformed the project's core claims into certified facts: friction reduced to 25% of standard steel cables; force estimation error <1% using only electrical resistance; "Golgi-like" passive force limiting.

2025-Unconventional Robotics Symposium

Unconventional Robotics Symposium, October 2025, TU Delft (NL). Contribution: "Superelastic Bowden-cable: a biomimetic solution for safer, more efficient assistive devices." This presentation positioned the ReMovAble transmission not only as a mechanical component but also as a biomimetic reflex system.

2025-Operational Continuity, Institutional Research

To bridge the critical gap between doctoral research and industrialization, the Department of Industrial Engineering (DIN) activated a dedicated funding. In July 2025, **Dr. Gregorio Pisaneschi** was awarded the Research Fellowship *"Study and development of biomedical devices"* financed by Prof. Andrea Zucchelli and Prof. Nicola Sancisi, transitioning project management from academic supervision to full-time technical leadership. This fellowship prevents the "Valley of Death" common in academic projects, securing 12 months of professional engineering time to translate the Patent and IEEE validation into a physical, clinically ready device.

Phase I (July '25 – Jan '26). Validated the "Phantom Hand" test bench for kinematic modeling and standardized the custom SMA sensing electronics, moving from breadboards to robust PCBs.

Phase II (Jan '26 – July '26). Following the official extension, the focus shifted to integrating the impedance control and sensorized SMA wires into a complete wearable device for laboratory trials.

University of Bologna

Advanced Materials & Design LAB

Superelastic Bowden-cable

a biomimetic solution for safer, more efficient assistive devices

Gregorio Pisaneschi, PhD

"Why not use your skills to help?"

Humanity-driven Engineering: creates impact, inspires action.

1 **Where does the need come from?**

The **ReMovAble** project: from the demand of **Montecatone Rehabilitation Clinic** to the design of a **hand assistive exoskeleton** for activities of daily life of tetraplegic people

The challenge

Precision in **traditional stiff mechanisms** comes with safety and efficiency limitations: potential failures due to cyclic loading, winding curvature and friction

- Reduced efficiency by up to 90%** [1]
- Safety and performance concerns** [2]

2 **How can we build assistive devices achieving inherent safety, efficiency, and human-like motion?**

- +** **Integration of sensors**
e.g. bending angle sensor
+ Compliant control
 - +** **Adding Mechanisms**
e.g. Variable Stiffn. Actuat.
 - +** **Compliant Design**
e.g. Shape Memory Alloy
 - Actuator Bowden cable [3]
 - Superelastic Bowden-cable
- Concept:** Development of a tendon sheath actuator based on a **superelastic Bowden cable (BC)** that **mimics a biological tendon**.

- **Inherent Safety:** Wire superelasticity mimics Golgi tendon protective reflex, by passive lengthening under overload.
- **Integrated Sensing** Wire electrical resistance changing provides feedback on strain and enable overload detection.

3 **Validation experiments: Material and Methods**

4 **Experiments: Results and Discussion**

5 **Findings and Future work**

- **Efficiency** : SE wire has 2x the efficiency of SS cable due to a low-friction, single-wire design.
- **Self-Sensing** : Integrated strain and overload detection (<1% error) via electrical resistance.
- **Self-limiting** : Superelasticity provides a fail-safe, triggering deactivation upon overload.

More Info @

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Figure 24 Unconventional Robotic Symposium Poster Contribution by Pisaneschi

2. Requirements, System Architecture & Objectives

2.1. Problem Statement

The GLOVE project addresses the significant challenges faced by individuals with **tetraplegia resulting from C6-C7 level spinal cord injuries**. This level of injury typically leads to **loss of hand function**. Patients experience paralysis or severe weakness in their hands, resulting in the inability to voluntarily open and close their fingers, make a fist, or perform fine motor tasks. This directly impacts their capacity to grasp, hold, and manipulate objects.

The loss of hand function severely **limits** the patient's ability to perform essential **Activities of Daily Living (ADLs)** independently, such as eating, drinking, writing, personal hygiene, and using common tools or devices. Consequently, patients often become heavily reliant on caregivers for assistance with most daily tasks, leading to a diminished sense of autonomy and independence. The inability to perform simple tasks and the increased dependence can significantly reduce the patient's overall quality of life, affecting their psychological well-being, social participation, and potential for vocational activities.

Specific Capabilities/Limitations

Preserved: all shoulder movements, pronation (inward rotation), wrist flexion and abduction (only in some), and elbow flexion through the use of the biceps, but not extension because of the weakened triceps.

Lost/Impaired: Paralysis of hand muscles, triceps (elbow extension), and often wrist flexors. Sensation in the hands is also commonly impaired or lost.

Figure 25 a) Elbow flexion, b) Wrist pronation, c) Wrist flexion, d) Wrist abduction; on the right, video with the patient of the clinic of Montecatone made by Paola Pagliarini

2.2. Requirements, clinic and current projects

The requirements for the GLOVE exoskeleton have evolved from initial clinical needs and have been refined through the iterative design, prototyping, and testing documented in the various GLOVE project theses.

Clinic Requirements, from Montecatone Rehabilitation Institute

- **Target Patient Population.** The device must be designed for patients with tetraplegia due to C6-C7 spinal cord injuries.
- **Affordability.** A key driver is to develop a significantly more affordable solution compared to existing commercial exoskeletons (target < €1000).
- **Functional Goal.** The primary function is to assist with basic hand movements
 - Primarily opening and closing the hand, to enable the **grasping** and releasing of everyday objects for ADLs (e.g., holding a glass, a phone).
 - Secondly, performing a **pinch** grip (e.g. for holding a pen, a card)
 - In addition to the closing and opening position, the exoskeleton should be configured to stay in a neutral **resting position** to not stress the hand and avoid discomfort for the patient while not in operation.
 - Need for active hand **opening** functionality (not only passive via springs, to avoid non-neutral positions and permit a wider opening for grasping)
- **Ergonomics goals.** The device should be easy to use, adjustable, non-invasive, comfortable and portable.
 - The device should be **simple** and intuitive to operate.
 - The control and actuation methods should be as **non-invasive** as possible (e.g. vocal commands were initially discarded as a primary sensory control system for the actuation for this reason).
 - The wearable component must be **comfortable** for potentially prolonged periods of use.
 - The exoskeleton should be **adaptable** to different hand sizes and potentially to the evolving needs of the patient.
 - The device must be inherently **safe** for the user, preventing injury.
 - The system should be **portable** to allow use in various environments, not just a clinical setting. The actuation unit might be wheelchair-mountable (e.g. POLY EXO GLOVE) or carried (e.g. TENOEXO).

Emergent Requirements, from Thesis and Research Works

Through detailed research, design iterations, and experimental work, the following specific requirements have emerged for the distinct subsystems of the device.

I. Control Signal System

- **Input and Intent Recognition**
 - Primary control modality for **actuation**: after clinic and patient feedback, Surface Electromyography (sEMG) from the patient's bicep muscle, leveraging preserved voluntary movement capabilities. Cost-effectiveness and ease of use are prioritised.
 - Secondary control as a **safety backup**: must be simple and reliable (e.g. a pressure or vocal sensor or a button). A physical button has been used as a secondary input method, and voice control can be implemented as an alternative, as suggested by the patient and the doctor, potentially leveraging smartphone speech recognition.
- **Signal Quality and Robustness**
 - EMG signals effective translation into **ON/OFF** commands for the exoskeleton's actuation control (or proportional activation in future).
 - EMGs are low-amplitude signals and need to be **amplified**. Robustly **filter out noise** to produce a clean signal (e.g. RMS).
 - Account for and mitigate known **EMG limitations**, such as subject dependency, electrode positioning sensitivity, and muscle fatigue.
 - Reliably **differentiate** predefined **voluntary muscle contraction** patterns (used for commands) from other muscle activity. For instance, using the contralateral bicep (non-dominant arm) provided clearer, more reliable command signals than the ipsilateral arm
- **Signal Processing and Pattern Recognition**
 - **Real-time** signal acquisition and processing are essential.
 - state machine logic for recognising specific **contraction patterns** (e.g., one long contraction for closure, two short contractions for opening).
 - User-specific calibration of EMG **activation thresholds** to accommodate individual differences in signal strength and muscle fatigue.
 - A mechanism for easy **adjustment of thresholds** (e.g., trimmer).
- **Hardware & Ergonomics**
 - Microcontroller with **Analog-to-Digital Converters** (ADC) capabilities and sufficient processing power. Adequate sampling rate for the EMG.
 - EMG sensor should be **non-invasive, comfortable, stable**, and suitable for prolonged daily wear, and manageable for tetraplegic patients to **don** and **doff** (possibly with assistance).
 - The system should provide clear and **intuitive feedback** to the user regarding its status (e.g., connection, battery level) and operation (e.g.,

hand opening/closing, threshold settings), possibly through vibrations or a simple display.

- A **safety lock/unlock feature** (e.g., physical button, voice command) to prevent unintended exoskeleton activations.

II. Actuation System

- **Motor Selection and Control Architecture**
 - **Actuator Type:** coreless DC micromotor for its good dynamics, compact size, and suitability for the application. Most works use this type of motor. The best solution would be **low-noise** and suitable for **force control**.
 - **Control Structure:** Refined cascaded control architecture managing torque/current (innermost loop), velocity (middle loop), and position (outer loop) with PID controllers at each level.
 - **Impedance control layer:** an additional impedance control loop is implemented to enable compliant interaction with variable loads, allowing adaptive force response during object grasping.
- **Power Transmission and Force Delivery**
 - **Convert** the motor's high-speed, low-torque output to low-speed, high-torque hand actuation via gearbox and pulley distribution system.
 - **Target performance:** ~20 N for closure, ~50 N for sustained grip; linear displacement 10–30 mm (hand-dependent); speed ~10 mm/s.
 - Bowden cable transmission integrated for lightweight, flexible force transmission to the wearable exoskeleton.
 - **Superelastic SMA Bowden cable:** Offers dual benefits, sensing via electrical resistance monitoring (force feedback within 1% error) and inherent passive force-limiting behaviour that mimics biological tendon protection, enhancing safety during unexpected collisions or overloads.
- **Safety and Feedback Control**
 - Accurate **encoder**-based position and velocity feedback.
 - Reliable **homing** procedure using physical end-stops for known reference position upon startup.
 - **Smooth motion** profiles to ensure natural actuation.
 - **Current/torque limits** for safety, preventing motor damage and ensuring safe interaction forces.
 - Accurate **current sensing** for the torque control loop, overload protection, and potentially for detecting object grasp.

III. Transmission and Exoskeleton Design

- **Transmission System**
 - guarantee the transmission from the portable actuator to the exoskeleton with a **lightweight solution** (e.g. tendon-driven, Bowden cables).

- **Underactuated:** single motor, multiple fingers/tendons, need a distribution system (e.g. pulleys).
- **Cable routing optimization:** Refined pathway design minimizing friction and preventing kinking, validated through kinematic and force analysis
- **Exoskeleton Ergonomics and Wearability**
 - Primary concerns: ensure device **safety**, respect the **natural movements** of the hand and prevent injuries to the user, enable a firm and secure **grip** on everyday objects (e.g. high friction material).
 - **Comfort and fit for prolonged daily wear:** based on individual patient anatomy (e.g. 3D scanning and 3D printing), **breathability** integrated into design, smooth edges, no pinching points.
 - **Simple to use**, intuitive. The exoskeleton must be easily accepted by patients, with a design that does not make them feel incapable.
 - **Easy donning/doffing** worn, used and removed by the patient independently, if possible ("top-down" application).
 - **Durability** for daily use; **modular** design enabling component replacement and **maintenance**. While based on standard anthropometric data for initial design, the system should be **adaptable** or **customizable** to individual user dimensions and needs.
- **Mechanical Structure & Materials**
 - **Hybrid soft-rigid design:** flexible materials (TPU, elastics) for comfort and fit; rigid elements (3D-printed finger rings, cable guides) for structural support and force transmission. **3D-printed** components enable patient-specific customization and rapid iteration.
 - **Lightweight** target: < 0.5 kg (~hand weight) to minimize user burden.
 - **Non-obtrusive, compact design.** exoskeleton height ≤ 1 cm (per clinicians' suggestion) above fingers to avoid interference with grasping.
- **Finger Guidance and Movement**
 - **Compliant joint mechanisms:** guide fingers naturally without restricting range of motion (sliding flexure for stress distribution and efficiency).
 - Flexure must **align** as possible with natural joint rotation centers and must be able to **spring back** fingers to a resting or open position after actuation and should be possible to move between these positions.
 - All actuated fingers must function seamlessly; **non-actuated fingers must not interfere** with grasping.
- **Thumb Integration.** Initial approaches involve **passive splinting** in an opposable position, with **adjustability** (e.g. assume two different configurations for pinching and grasping). Future development: Full active thumb actuation for enhanced grasping versatility.

Additional Clinical Context

Tetraplegic patients with C6-C7 injuries lack residual hand strength and rely entirely on the exoskeleton for force generation. However, they retain passive hand manipulation capability (e.g., skin adhesion and wrist flexion enable holding objects weighing ~0.5 kg without assistance). Preserved motor capabilities in the bicep and partial wrist strength provide the input signals and any supplementary control modalities. The device must be inherently safe, intuitive, and foster user acceptance and dignity.

Figure 26 The patient at the clinic is trying the prototype TRE

2.3. Objectives, new project

The **primary objective** is to create a new **functional prototype** that **responds to the requirements and solves previous challenges**.

The **secondary objective** is to **validate the self-limiting and self-sensing capabilities** of a **superelastic Bowden cable in an exoskeleton**.

2026 – Removable QUATTRO, design and prototyping

The overarching objective of the project is to develop a functional, user-friendly, and affordable hand exoskeleton for individuals with C6-C7 tetraplegia. The specific objectives are summarised below and will be further defined during the project.

Project-Level Objectives

- **Improve Patient Quality of Life:** The aim is to enhance independence, autonomy, and overall quality of life for individuals living with tetraplegia.

- **Develop an Affordable Assistive Device:** Keep development and potential production costs significantly lower than existing commercial alternatives (target < €1000).
- **Create an Integrated and Robust System:** Seamlessly combines control signal processing, motor actuation, force transmission, and wearable design into a reliable, user-accepted prototype.
- **Clinical Validation:** Conduct validation trials with one or more patients to rigorously evaluate the exoskeleton's effectiveness, usability, and impact
- **Establish a Research Platform:** Create a prototype that serves as a foundation for ongoing research into EMG-based control, advanced transmission systems, and human-machine interaction in assistive devices.

Functional Objectives

- **Restore Basic Hand Functions:** opening and closing of at least the index and middle fingers (and ideally the thumb) to allow for effective grasping and releasing of common objects (the other fingers must not interfere).
- **Enable Independent Operation:** Allow the patient to control the exoskeleton intuitively and to easily tune functions and configurations.
- **Provide Sufficient and Safe Grip Force:** Deliver adequate force for secure grasping while incorporating mechanisms to prevent excessive force application.
- **Versatile Grasp Types:** Support cylindrical/power grasp initially; design must accommodate or be adaptable to pinch grasp and other common grip patterns.
- **User Comfort and Acceptance:** Maximize comfort for extended daily wear; simplify donning/doffing; create a device that users accept without feeling incapacitated or burdened

Technical Objectives (by Subsystem)

A. Control Signal System

- Evaluate **commercial EMG** sensors (Delsys Trigno Avanti) **versus custom**-designed solutions in terms of robustness, shielding, integration complexity, and cost.
- Complete **hardware assembly and PCB prototyping** of the custom EMG sensor; refine analog filtering and noise rejection circuits.
- Implement **robust state-machine-based pattern recognition** to reliably distinguish user commands from movement artefacts, particularly leveraging the contralateral arm for clearer signals.

- Develop user-friendly **calibration** mechanisms (software or mechanical adjustment) for **threshold** personalization and **adaptive tuning** to adjust to the user's changing physiological state (e.g., muscle fatigue).
- **Enhance the EMG control** system's ability to reliably distinguish user commands from movement artefacts, especially in dynamic, real-world scenarios (e.g. explore adaptive algorithms and integrated IMU).

Advanced Development:

- **Multi-modal integration:** Explore hybrid control combining EMG with integrated IMU data to further distinguish intentional commands from functional arm movements.
- **Adaptive algorithms:** Develop systems that autonomously adjust thresholds and recognition parameters as muscle fatigue or signal properties change during extended use.

B. Actuation System

- **Motor selection and control validation:** Evaluate and select the optimal motor solution (commercial options or refined Faulhaber setup) and determine if single or multiple motors are required for back-and-forth actuation of multiple fingers.
- **Cascaded control refinement:** Finalize tuning of torque/current, velocity, and position control loops based on D'Agostino's 2025 work; achieve close alignment between MATLAB simulations and real prototype behavior.
- **Impedance control implementation:** Fully integrate the impedance control layer to enable compliant, safe interaction during object grasping and unexpected contact.
- **Position tracking and smooth motion:** Ensure precise control of exoskeleton hand configurations (fully open, fully closed, neutral resting positions) with smooth, natural motion profiles.
- **Robust safety mechanisms:** Implement homing procedures, current limits, and torque constraints for inherent safety.

Advanced Development:

- **Superelastic Bowden cable integration:** Validate and operationalize the patented SE SMA Bowden cable transmission in the exoskeleton, leveraging its self-sensing and self-limiting capabilities for advanced force feedback and collision detection.

- **Force feedback for grasp control:** Implement superelastic Bowden resistance-based or force-sensor feedback to enable proportional grasp force control.

C. Exoskeleton Design

- **QFD-guided design:** Apply findings from previous Quality Function Deployment analysis, focusing on comfort, ease of wear, cleanability, and accessibility.
- **Patient-specific customization:** Utilize 3D hand scanning and modeling to create anatomically fitted palm and dorsal support structures; refine finger ring design for improved breathability, sturdiness, and cable guidance.
- **Passive return mechanism:** Design, optimize and integrate a seamless passive return mechanism (via compliant joints, elastic elements, or shaped SMA wires) enabling natural hand opening.
- **Bowden cable integration:** Optimize cable channel and guide design within the glove structure to minimize friction, prevent kinking, and ensure efficient force transmission.
- **Modular construction:** Design finger rings, cable terminations, and palm support as replaceable modules facilitating maintenance, cleaning, and component updates.
- **Comfort and wearability trials:** Conduct iterative fitting trials with target patients, gathering qualitative and quantitative feedback on comfort, pressure points, breathability, and ease of use.

Advanced Development:

- **Thumb actuation:** Transition from passive splinting to active thumb control, expanding grasp versatility.
- **Material innovation:** Explore advanced materials (soft robotics, textile integration) for improved comfort and aesthetic acceptance.
- **Miniaturization and integration:** Develop more compact, self-contained designs incorporating battery storage and all electronics into a seamless wearable system.

2026–Superelastic Bowden, design and prototyping

The overarching objective is to **validate the concept of usability as self-limiting and self-sensing**, also expressed in the patent, in a case scenario similar to the **real use**. Following the detailed objectives. **Under cyclic and dynamic loading conditions in an exoskeleton:**

- **validate sensing:** experimentally confirm that electrical resistance of SE SMA wires accurately reflects force transmission
- **validate self-limiting:** Demonstrate that stress-induced martensitic transformation provides intrinsic force-limiting capability;
- **develop feedback control:** implement and validate resistance-based feedback control loops enabling collision detection and force regulation without dedicated force sensors;
- **test closed-Loop System:** test the SE Bowden cable, measuring simultaneous force, displacement, and electrical resistance to establish reliable force-resistance relationships.

2.4. Key Success Metrics

- **Functional:** Demonstrate reliable hand opening/closing with ≥ 20 N grip force, ≤ 1 cm height profile, actuation speed ~ 10 mm/s.
- **Control:** EMG command recognition accuracy $\geq 90\%$ in patient trials; cascaded control tracking error $< 5\%$; impedance control stability under variable loads.
- **Usability:** Donning/doffing time < 5 minutes; patient comfort rating $\geq 4/5$; intuitive control requiring < 1 hour training.
- **Safety:** No device-related adverse events; force limiting reliably activates at threshold; homing and emergency stop functions 100% reliable.
- **Clinical:** Statistically significant improvement in patient independence metrics for ADLs; positive feedback from clinical team.